

Regeneration of anther-derived callus

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We tested four differentiation media for numbers of regenerates with green and multiple shoots from anther-derived callus. Nine indica varieties and five F₂ crosses of deep water rice were used.

Single calli cultured from each variety were inoculated with three to five replications of the differentiation media. Gamborg's basic medium with 4% sucrose and different kinds and concentrations of growth regulators was used to regenerate anther-derived callus.

D2 and D3 were best for green plant

regeneration (Table 1). However, D3 with adenine sulfate (AD) in addition to other growth regulators produced more multiple shoots. Adding naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) or benzylamino purine (BA) increased the number of green shoots. Degeneration of callus or dead tissue formation occurred in all media tested.

D3 was further tested with callus cultured from five F₂ crosses of deep water rice. Although it gave rise to albino shoots, the production of multiple shoots per callus was confirmed (Table 2). Single plants from the multiple shoots were grown into individual plants. The results indicate a varietal difference in regeneration ability and green shoot production. No single medium seems to be best for a wide range of genotypes. □

Table 2. Regeneration from anther-derived callus of 5 F₂ crosses of deep water rice in a specific medium.^a Gazipur, Bangladesh.

Variety	D3					
	g	a	r	mg	ma	d
IR43141 (BR525-2-1/ IR19672-155-2-11-3)	-	-	1	6	-	-
IR43126 (BR314-B-4-6/ DWCT 156-1-B-B)	1	-	1	3	-	-
IR43131 (BR311-B-5-4/ IR13429-299-2-1-3)	1	4	-	1	4	-
IR43615 (IR10110-23-1// BR222-B-249/RD19)	-	-	-	-	-	1
IR43841 (BR223-B-55- H2-B-RD19/BR576-331-1// IR11288-B-B-118-1)	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total	2	4	2	10	4	2

^a D3 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 BA + 5.0 AD + 1.0 K + 0.5 IAA. g = single green shoot, a = single albino shoot, r = root, mg = multiple green shoots callus, ma = multiple albino shoot, d = dead tissue, - = slight or no callus growth.

Table 1. Regeneration from anther-derived callus in 4 regeneration media.^a Gazipur, Bangladesh.

Variety	D0					D1					D2					D3							
	g	a	r	mg	ma	d	g	a	r	mg	ma	dg	a	r	mg	ma	dg	a	r	mg	ma	d	
BR9-HR7	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
CNM-20	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	3	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
BR601-3-3-4-2-2	-	-	1	-	-	5	-	2	1	-	4	3	-	1	-	3	-	-	1	-	-	4	
IR29692-65-2-3	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	
BR562-23-1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	4	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	
IR13240-108-2-2-3	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	-	1	20	-
Delta	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cul 25315	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	2	1	3	2	-	1	-	1	4	-
Calrose	1	-	2	1	1	1	-1	p	2	-	11	1	-	lp	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	2
Total	1	0	7	1	1	14	0	5	6	-	22	13	3	4	4	3	2	9	2	1	3	5	20

^a D0 = Gamborg's (BS) + 4% sucrose, D1 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 K + 1.0 IAA, D2 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.25 NAA + 1.0 K + 0.25 IAA, and D3 = Gamborg's (B5) + 4% sucrose + 0.5 BAP + 5.0 AD + 1.0 K + 0.5 IAA. g = single green shoot, a = single albino shoot, p = purple shoot, r = root, mg = multiple green shoot, ma = multiple albino shoot, d = dead tissue, - = only slight growth or no growth of callus.

Multiple reciprocal translocation from somatic cell culture in IR54

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We found a multiple chromosome reciprocal translocation (MRT), involving five nonhomologous chromosomes, from somatic cell culture of IR54. Young panicles were cultured in MS medium (sucrose 6%) with 1 mg 2,4-D and 1 mg

kinetin/liter. The callus was subcultured for one passage and transferred to MS medium (sucrose 3%) with 2 mg NAA and 2 mg kinetin/liter for regeneration.

One MRT plant was found in the regenerated plants. It was shorter than IR54 and its anther did not split during flowering. The pollen grains were almost empty and not stained by I-KI. No seeds were set under selfing; some seeds were set under crossing.

Chromosome behavior in meiosis of

pollen mother cells (PMC) was abnormal. Bivalents at diakinesis numbered 6 to 12. Only 5.7% of the cells had 12II at diakinesis. Various multivalent configurations were observed at diakinesis, such as tetravalents (10II + 1IV or 8II + 2IV or 6II + 3IV), hexavalents (9II + 1VI or 7II + 1IV + 1VI or 6II + 2VI), octavalents (8II + 1VIII or 6II + 1IV + 1VIII), and tenvalents (7II + 1X) (see table). The tenvalents were present either as a ring or as a chain (see

Chromosome conjugation at diakinesis. Guangzhou, China.

Chromosome conjugation	12II	10II	9II	8II	8II	7II	7II ^a	6II	6II	6II	Total
		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
						11V			11V		
						+			+		
		11V	1VI	1VIII	2IV	1VI	1X	3IV	1VIII	2VI	
Frequency	25	15	29	36	27	61	223	10	9	5	438
%	5.70	2.96	6.62	8.21	6.16	13.9	50.91	2.28	2.05	1.14	

^aRing-shaped tenvalent (7II + S) = 107,48%. Chain-shaped tenvalent (7II + 1 10) = 116, 52%.

figure). The maximum number of chromosomes in the ring-shaped configuration was tenvalent.

Ring-shaped chromosome configurations at diakinesis and sterile pollen grains and seeds are the major

characters of reciprocal translocation heterozygotes. The tenvalent ring showed that the reciprocal translocations involved 5 nonhomologous chromosome pairs. □

7II + 1 (10) (top) at diakinesis and 5II + 11V + 1X (bottom) at metaphase I. Guangzhou, China.

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Influence of *Trichoconiella padwickii* on seed germination and seedling growth in rice

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Trichoconiella padwickii is a common rice seed fungus, particularly when harvesting is at high atmospheric humidity. The effect of the fungus on seed germination and shoot length, and the symptoms produced were studied using the soil inoculation technique. A 1% inoculum was incorporated in the first 10 cm of soil. Sterilized seeds of Cauvery, Benibhog,

Influence of *T. padwickii* on seed germination and shoot length. Bihar, India.

Variety	Seed germination (%)			Shoot length		
	Control	<i>T. padwickii</i> inoculated	Reduction	Control (m)	<i>T. padwickii</i> inoculated (cm)	Reduction (%)
Mahsuri	80	46	57.5	5.6	3.9	69.6
Cauvery	81	46	56.8	4.9	3.3	67.3
Jaya	84	44	52.4	5.7	3.4	59.6
IR20	79	41	51.9	5.4	3.1	57.4
Benibhog	78	42	53.8	5.2	2.8	53.8
CD 5%		1.4			0.3	
CV (%)		2.3			1.9	

Jaya, IR20, and Mahsuri were planted. All five varieties showed significant reductions in seed germination and

shoot length (see table). The maximum reduction in seed germination and shoot length was in Mahsuri. □

Across-season survival of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, causal agent of bacterial leaf streak (BLS)

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BLS is caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*. We studied its survival cycle in India.

During the Jun-Nov season, Assam Rice Collection entries at AICRIP

farm were severely affected by BLS. Seeds of 12 severely affected cultivars were harvested, sun-dried, and stored at room temperature. Part of this seed was sown in the following Dec-Apr season and observed for disease development. None of the 12 cultivars showed BLS symptoms. In the following Jun-Nov season, part of the old BLS-infected seed and freshly harvested BLS-free seed were planted in isolated fields to avoid external contamination.

BLS appeared in the infested seed only, not in the newly harvested disease-free Dec-Apr season seed. This confirms seed transmission of BLS from one summer season to the next.

It also indicates the inability of the disease to be established during the cool dry weather winter season. The disease cycle is broken if summer seed is sown in the winter season, but not if it is kept for the following summer season. □